

Rare land snails from the Faroe Islands (Denmark): first records for the archipelago or single islands

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Abstract. The Faroe Islands, an isolated North Atlantic archipelago, are characterized by a grassland vegetation, which is shaped by strong winds and, since human settlement, also by intensive sheep grazing. This study, conducted in August 2023, investigated terrestrial gastropod fauna across 46 sites on six islands: Vagár, Streymoy, Eysturoy, Kunoy, Borðoy, and Viðoy. We found 26 gastropod species, including two new species for the archipelago (*Euconulus fulvus* and *Vertigo angustior*). Several rare species were found at new locations, including *Lauria cylindracea*, previously only known from a single site on Suðuoy, now documented at two additional sites on Vagár and Streymoy. Species richness at the sites varied between 1 and 16 species, with an average of five species. The fauna is notably slug-dominated, as on average more slug species were found at a site than snail species. Our results illustrate the effects of overgrazing by sheep, which limits gastropod diversity to refuges such as steep rocky outcrops, tall riparian vegetation in narrow canyons, and less disturbed wetlands. The snail fauna of the Faroes is relatively species-poor (31 species in total) and is dominated by introduced generalists and non-native slugs, while micro-snails, which are common in other insular areas with similar climates, are notably absent.

Key words. Mollusca, Gastropoda, survey, snails, slugs, distribution

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INTRODUCTION

The Faroe Islands, an isolated archipelago in the North Atlantic between Iceland and Scotland, consist of 18 rugged volcanic islands characterized by steep cliffs and fjords. The islands are exposed remnants of the extensive Palaeogene basalt lava flows (Millett *et al.* 2017), with modern soils that generally have low base saturation due to intensive leaching (Veihe & Thers 2007). The islands are of a predominantly maritime climate, experiencing cool summers (12–15 °C on average) and mild winters (3–5 °C) with frequent rainfall (1,270 mm annually). The natural growth of trees is prevented in particular by the persistently strong winds. As a result, the landscape on most of the islands is dominated by grassland and rare shrubs; only a few trees are planted. The Norse settlers arrived in the 9th century and introduced sheep, efficient grazers that changed the landscape considerably (Jóhansen 1985; Mysterud & Thórhallsdóttir 2016). Today, the number of sheep is greater than the human population. Their grazing pressure reduces plant diversity and

biomass, especially of tall herbs and shrubs, and it also contributes to erosion (McGovern *et al.* 2005; Lawson *et al.* 2008; Verbrugge *et al.* 2022). Nowadays, most of the area resembles a well-maintained golf course, albeit with sheep droppings scattered across the landscape.

To date, 29 species of land snails and slugs have been reported from the archipelago (Fog 1971; Solhøy 1981), of which at least eight have been recently introduced by humans (McMillan 1972; Jensen *et al.* 2014). In the past, two large field surveys have been conducted on all islands, documenting 22 species mainly between 1925–1926 (Fog 1971) and 20 species (Solhøy 1981). While most species (*c.* 75%) are distributed throughout the archipelago, five occur only in a few localities, with *Lauria cylindracea* known only from a single locality on Suðuoy (Fog 1971). Although the fauna appears to be well recorded in terms of native elements, no systematic inventory of non-anthropogenic habitats has been published in the last 45 years.

Here we report the results of our research in 2023 on six islands that are accessible by car, with an aim to capture the

highest possible diversity of natural habitats suitable for the occurrence of terrestrial gastropods.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In August 2023, we surveyed the terrestrial gastropod fauna at 46 sites on six of the islands: Vagár, Streymoy, Eysturoy, Kunoy, Borðoy, and Viðoy. Snails and slugs were collected by hand, litter sieving or wet sieving in spring fens and other wetlands (Horsák 2003). Samples were air-dried at room temperature, identified, and counted. They are deposited in the collection of M. Horsák in Brno, Czech Republic. Images of voucher individuals were taken using an Olympus szx 7 microscope with Olympus C-7070 wide zoom camera and QuickPHOTO MICRO software at c. 20×. Between five and ten images were taken with the focus from the bot-

tom to the top of the shell and merged into a single focussed image using Combine ZM (<https://combinezm.en.lo4d.com/windows>). Boxplots were created using the 'ggplot2' package in R (Wickham 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During our field study, 26 terrestrial gastropod species were recorded (Table 1), including *Euconulus fulvus* and *Vertigo angustior*, which are new to the archipelago (Table 2; Figs 1, 2). We also extended the known distribution of the other five rare species. *Lauria cylindracea* was originally reported from a single site on the island of Suðuoy; however, we found it at two new sites on the islands of Vagár and Streymoy (Table 2). Abundant colonies were found at natural habitats with a species-rich (by Faroese standards) snail fauna. The spe-

Table 1. All recorded land snail and slug species across 46 sites sampled on six road-connected islands of the Faroe archipelago. Frequency, number of sites with the species occurrence; No. islands, the number of islands where the species was found during our survey; No. total, the combined total number of islands where the species was recorded in previous surveys (Fog 1971; McMillan 1972; Solhøy 1981; Jensen *et al.* 2014) and our survey. There are 18 islands in the archipelago, but no data exist from Lítla Dímun, the smallest island.

Species	Frequency	No. islands	No. total
<i>Arion distinctus</i> Mabile, 1868	22	5	13
<i>Vitrea contracta</i> (Westerlund, 1871)	19	3	14
<i>Oxychilus alliarius</i> (J. S. Miller, 1822)	19	3	17
<i>Arion fuscus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	18	3	16
<i>Perpolita hammonis</i> (Strøm, 1765)	18	4	9
<i>Arion silvaticus</i> Lohmander, 1937	16	4	15
<i>Arion vulgaris</i> Moquin-Tandon, 1855	14	2	3
<i>Columella aspera</i> Waldén, 1966	12	4	12
<i>Lehmannia marginata</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	11	3	17
<i>Deroceras laeve</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	10	4	9
<i>Arion ater</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	9	3	16
<i>Deroceras agreste</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	3	16
<i>Vitrea pellucida</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	7	3	17
<i>Arion intermedius</i> Normand, 1852	6	2	17
<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	6	3	5
<i>Deroceras invadens</i> Reise <i>et al.</i> , 2011	6	2	2
<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i> (Draparnaud, 1805)	5	3	5
<i>Deroceras reticulatum</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	5	2	17
<i>Aegopinella pura</i> (Alder, 1830)	4	3	6
<i>Euconulus fulvus</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	3	2	2
<i>Lauria cylindracea</i> (Da Costa, 1778)	3	2	3
<i>Arianta arbustorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2	1	4
<i>Arion fasciatus</i> (Nilsson, 1823)	2	1	1
<i>Oxychilus cellarius</i> (O.F. Müller, 1774)	2	1	3
<i>Punctum pygmaeum</i> (Draparnaud, 1801)	2	2	15
<i>Vertigo angustior</i> Jeffreys, 1830	1	1	1

Table 2. List of new records with location information. Live, number of live individuals; shell, number of empty shells found. Collector for all: Horsák and Horsáková.

Site ID	Species	Live	Shell	Island	Lat (°N)	Lon (°W)	Settlement	Habitat	Date
FAE41/23	<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i>	0	2	Streymoy	61.9486	006.7797	Kirkjubøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	13.08.2023
FAE12/23	<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i>	7	6	Streymoy	61.9505	006.7840	Kirkjubøur	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	06.08.2023
FAE14/23	<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i>	1	0	Streymoy	62.0558	006.9224	Norðradalur	Spring fen along a brook	06.08.2023
FAE36/23	<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i>	4	3	Vágar	62.0850	007.3628	Bøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	11.08.2023
FAE24/23	<i>Aegopinella nitidula</i>	2	4	Eysturoy	62.1908	006.7493	Gøtugjógv	Tall-herb vegetation in a canyon	08.08.2023
FAE12/23	<i>Aegopinella pura</i>	1	0	Streymoy	61.9505	006.7840	Kirkjubøur	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	06.08.2023
FAE13/23	<i>Aegopinella pura</i>	6	0	Streymoy	62.0163	006.9075	Syðradalur	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	06.08.2023
FAE36/23	<i>Aegopinella pura</i>	1	0	Vágar	62.0850	007.3628	Bøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	11.08.2023
FAE32/23	<i>Aegopinella pura</i>	9	2	Eysturoy	62.2912	007.0784	Eiði	Herb vegetation in a canyon	10.08.2023
FAE41/23	<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i>	2	2	Streymoy	61.9486	006.7797	Kirkjubøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	13.08.2023
FAE12/23	<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i>	7	5	Streymoy	61.9505	006.7840	Kirkjubøur	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	06.08.2023
FAE37/23	<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i>	1	0	Vágar	62.1184	007.4265	Gásadalur	Productive spring fen	12.08.2023
FAE15/23	<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i>	7	1	Streymoy	62.1450	007.1770	Vestmanna	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	07.08.2023
FAE32/23	<i>Cochlicopa lubrica</i>	19	1	Eysturoy	62.2912	007.0784	Eiði	Herb vegetation in a canyon	10.08.2023
FAE11/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	6	0	Streymoy	61.9665	006.8194	Velbastaður	Wet pasture with shrubs	06.08.2023
FAE42/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	20	0	Streymoy	61.9994	006.8237	Tórshavn	Artificial willow growth	13.08.2023
FAE22/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	2	0	Eysturoy	62.1878	006.7596	Syðrugøta	Artificial willow growth	08.08.2023
FAE09/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	2	0	Streymoy	62.1880	007.0354	Hvalvík	Artificial wetland forest	05.08.2023
FAE23/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	1	0	Eysturoy	62.1921	006.7517	Gøtugjógv	Artificial maple growth	08.08.2023
FAE28/23	<i>Deroceras invadens</i>	4	0	Streymoy	62.2850	007.1016	Haldórsvík	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	09.08.2023
FAE14/23	<i>Euconulus fulvus</i>	5	0	Streymoy	62.0558	006.9224	Norðradalur	Spring fen along a brook	06.08.2023
FAE15/23	<i>Euconulus fulvus</i>	3	1	Streymoy	62.1449	007.1770	Vestmanna	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	07.08.2023
FAE32/23	<i>Euconulus fulvus</i>	25	3	Eysturoy	62.2912	007.0784	Eiði	Herb vegetation in a canyon	10.08.2023
FAE41/23	<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	8	3	Streymoy	61.9486	006.7797	Kirkjubøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	13.08.2023
FAE12/23	<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	32	19	Streymoy	61.9505	006.7840	Kirkjubøur	Wet rocks with rich vegetation	06.08.2023
FAE36/23	<i>Lauria cylindracea</i>	26	19	Vágar	62.0850	007.3628	Bøur	Mesic-dry rocks, rich vegetation	11.08.2023
FAE08/23	<i>Vertigo angustior</i>	0	1	Streymoy	62.2358	007.1437	Saksun	Alkaline spring fen	05.08.2023

Figure 1. Location of new sites for seven rare terrestrial gastropod species on the Faroe Islands, including old records from previous publications (Fog 1971; McMillan 1972; Solhøy 1981). Map adopted from <https://www.vectorstock.com>.

Figure 2. Images of voucher specimens of the two newly reported micro-land snails from the Faroe Islands: **A**, *Euconulus fulvus*, #FAE32/23, Eysturoy, Eiði (Breiðá), rich herb vegetation in a river canyon; **B**, *Vertigo angustior*, #FAE08/23, Streymoy, Oyranar (Dalá), a small rich fen. Photos: M. Horsák.

cies was restricted to the dense and preserved vegetation of rocky outcrops on very steep slopes that cannot be grazed by sheep. After learning the correct vegetation architecture (Fig. 3C, D), we discovered the second locality at Vagár by searching with binoculars in the same type of cliff-edge vegetation. Therefore, it is likely that the species is more common but restricted to hard-to-reach places that require specialised climbing equipment and a lot of effort to reach. However, it is likely that only sites enriched with calcium through intense weathering or base-rich seepages can support a richer malacofauna, including also more demanding snail species. The homogeneous volcanic bedrock, which is usually overlain by acidic soils due to intensive leaching (Veihe & Thers 2007), is probably also an additional pre-

Figure 3. Images of sampled sites. **A**, a larger complex of alkaline seepages and small spring fens with *Eriophorum angustifolium* and brown mosses in the valley of the Dalá River in Streymoy, site #FAE08/23 with *Vertigo angustior*. **B**, dense tall-herb riparian vegetation and shrubs in the narrow canyon near Gøtugjógv in Eysturoy, site #FAE24/23 with *Aegopinella nitidula*. **C**, **D**, layers of steep base-rich outcrops forming ledges with rich vegetation of rock shelves along the coast near Kirkjubøur in Streymoy, site #FAE12/23 with *Lauria cylindracea*, *Cochlicopa lubrica*, *A. nitidula*, and *A. pura* (the richest natural site with 15 terrestrial gastropod species). **E**, **F**, heavily overgrazed landscape supports mostly only slug populations. Photos: V. Horsáková.

dicator of land-snail distribution and local species richness, which is generally favoured by alkaline conditions (e.g. Horsák 2006).

We also investigated several fen habitats, which mostly developed on alkaline seepages on gentle slopes or along

small streams. We focussed on less overgrazed, more productive vegetation, as the heavily overgrazed vegetation typically only favoured the occurrence of slugs, hiding in old sheep stone shelters or under stones in general (Fig. 3E, F). We found three populations of *E. fulvus* (Fig. 2A)

on the islands of Streymoy (two sites) and Eysturoy (one site) in such habitats (Fig. 3B). In an extensive seepage area with many small alkaline fen pockets in the northern part of Streymoy (Fig. 3A), a single shell of *V. angustior* (Fig. 2B) was found in a quantitative 12-L wet sieve sample. Further research is required to determine the population of this species, which may be a victim of sheep grazing. This is the first record of a *Vertigo* species in the archipelago. The absence of other, otherwise common micro-snails in such habitats of the European Atlantic coast or the Shetland Islands is surprising. These common components of the maritime grassland snail fauna are completely absent (e.g. *Vallonia* spp.) and many of the species present, otherwise common generalists, are conspicuously rare, such as *E. fulvus*, *Vitrina pellucida*, and *Cochlicopa lubrica* (all common throughout Iceland; M. Horsák and V. Horsáková pers. observ.) The latter species has only been reported from five sites on the islands of Suðuoy and Sandoy (Solhøy 1981), but was also found on Vagár, Streymoy and Eysturoy (5 sites in total) during our sampling.

Interestingly, all 26 species recorded also occurred on Streymoy, the largest of all the islands, which lies in the centre of the archipelago. The species richness of the sites varied between 1 and 16 species, with an average of five species (Fig. 4). The most species-rich site, Viðarlundin í Hvalvík on Streymoy, was an artificial swamp forest with old willow and alder trees, fallen wood, and sedge vegetation along the streams. The second most species-rich site, Kirkjubøur on Streymoy (Fig. 3C, D), was a natural cliff face with vegetated ledges and base-rich seepages that harboured 15 species, including *A. nitidula*, *A. pura*, *C. lubrica*, and *L. cylindracea*.

The Faroese snail fauna is very sluggish, even in non-anthropogenic habitats. We documented 15 shelled snail species, including all previously reported species from the wild, and 11 slug species. The proportion of slug species in the gastropod assemblages was very high and varied between 20 and 100%, with an average of 60%. On average, there were more slug species than shelled snail species at one site (Fig. 4). In addition to nine slug species recorded by Solhøy (1981) between 1977 and 1979, *Deroceras invadens* was reported by McMillan (1972) to be common west of the capital Tórshavn. Two other non-native slug species, *Limax maximus* and *Arion vulgaris*, were recently reported by Jensen *et al.* (2014). While Solhøy (1981) and Jensen *et al.* (2014) did not list *D. invadens*, we found it at four sites on Streymoy (it was common near Tórshavn) and at two sites on Eysturoy. Although it was mostly found in man-made or heavily modified habitats such as artificially planted growths of willows and conifers, two sites were only slightly dis-

Figure 4. Variation of site species richness observed at 44 sampled sites; two sites with no land-snail species recorded were excluded.

turbed natural areas (Table 2). Solhøy (1981) also did not list *Arion fasciatus*, whereas it was mentioned by Fog (1971).

There are more sheep than people on the Faroe Islands, on average 50 ewes per km² (Thorsteinsson 2020). However, the density varies from area to area and ranges from 13 to 546 per km² (Verbrugge *et al.* 2022). Overgrazing by sheep has had a severe impact on ecosystems, in particular it has removed all native shrubs and dwarf willows from the landscape. The only places where these survive are inaccessible cliffs (Pálsson 1993). As a result, the occurrence of forest and shrub snail species is limited to a few refugia, again on rocky outcrops or in deep rocky ravines (Fig. 3B). These were the habitats of two *Aegopinella* species known from the Faroe Islands. *Aegopinella pura* was found at six sites on Suðuoy, Streymoy, Nólsoy, and Kunoy. We found another colony on Streymoy and two new sites on Vagár and Eysturoy. Likewise, *A. nitidula* was known from five sites on Suðuoy, Sandoy, and Streymoy (Solhøy 1981). We re-sampled a rich population at the southern tip of Streymoy (Fig. 3C) and also recorded a new site on Vagár and also on Eysturoy (Fig. 3B).

The fauna of the Faroe Islands is relatively species-poor—based on all surveys combined, 31 terrestrial gastropod species were recorded, of which at least eight were recently introduced by humans (Jensen *et al.* 2014). It is very likely that the majority of the remaining fauna has also been introduced by humans. Therefore, the fauna consists mainly of generalist and non-native temperate species, with only a few species whose colonisation could have been naturally medi-

ated by migratory birds (e.g. Simonová *et al.* 2016). There are several reasons for this, such as isolation (the Shetland Islands, 300 km away, are the closest land mass), the relatively small total area and the homogeneous geology and vegetation. In comparison, 43 species of land snails (including 13 slugs) are known from the Shetland, although these are only about 5% larger, have a milder climate and are less isolated. With the exception of *V. angustior*, the terrestrial gastropods of the Faroe Islands are a complete subset of the species found on Shetland. The lack of natural, more productive shrub and forest vegetation on the Faroes probably excludes many of the gastropod species found on Shetland. Following human colonisation, heavy overgrazing by sheep and soil erosion may have led to the extinction of some species and restricted many species to a few small and preserved sites as found also for *Pupilla alpicola* on Iceland (Horsák *et al.* 2022). This could explain the very scattered occurrence of some species that are common habitat generalists in European regions with similar climates (e.g. *C. lubrica*, *E. fulvus*, *V. pellucida*). This has also led to the establishment of a gastropod fauna that favours slug species, many of which, probably almost all, have been introduced by humans.

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REFERENCES

- FOG K. 1971. Land and freshwater Mollusca. Pp. 1–38 in: Spärck R, Tuxen SL (Eds) 1928–1971. *The Zoology of the Faroes III(I)*: LVII.
- HORSÁK M. 2003. How to sample mollusc communities in mires easily. *Malacologica Bohemoslovaca* **2**: 11–14. <https://doi.org/10.5817/MaB2002-2-11>
- HORSÁK M. 2006. Mollusc community patterns and species response curves along a mineral richness gradient: a case study in fens. *Journal of Biogeography* **33**: 98–107. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2005.01359.x>
- HORSÁK M, HORSÁKOVÁ V, DIVÍŠEK J, NEKOLA JC. 2022. Ecological niche divergence between extant and glacial land snail populations explained. *Scientific Reports* **12**: 806. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-04645-2>
- JENSEN JK, HANSEN JF, NOLSØ Á. 2015. Seven species of landsnails (Gastropoda) new to the Faroe Islands. *Fróðskaparrit-Farøese Scientific Journal* **61**: 191–209. <https://doi.org/10.18602/fsj.v0i61.20>
- JÓHANSEN J. 1985. Studies in the vegetational history of the Faroe and Shetland Islands. *Annales Societatis Scientiarum Faeroensis* (XI.) 117. Diploma thesis, Tórshavn.
- LAWSON IT, EDWARDS KJ, CHURCH MJ, NEWTON AJ, COOK GT, GATHORNE-HARDY FJ, DUGMORE AJ. 2008. Human impact on an island ecosystem: pollen data from Sandoy, Faroe Islands. *Journal of Biogeography* **35**: 1130–1152. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2007.01838.x>
- MCGOVERN TH, AMOROSI T, WOOLLETT J. 2005. Human impact and landscape degradation on the Faroe Islands. *Human Ecology* **33**: 651–684.
- MCMILLAN NF. 1972. *Agriolimax caruanae* Pollonera and other non-marine Mollusca in Faroe. *Journal of Conchology* **27**: 419–421.
- MILLET JM, HOLE MJ, JOLLEY DW, PASSEY SR. 2017. Geochemical stratigraphy and correlation within large igneous provinces: the final preserved stages of the Faroe Islands Basalt Group. *Lithos* **286**: 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2017.05.011>
- MYSTERUD A, THÓRHALLSDÓTTIR A G. 2016. Sheep grazing in the North Atlantic region: A long-term perspective on environmental sustainability. *Ambio* **45**: 551–566. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-016-0771-z>
- PÁLSSON J. 1993. *Salix arctica* Pall. and *Salix lanata* L. in the Faroe Islands and their affinity with the populations in Iceland. *Fróðskaparrit-Farøese Scientific Journal* **41**: 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.18602/fsj.v41i.629>
- SIMONOVÁ J, SIMON OP, KAPIC Š, NEHASIL L, HORSÁK M. 2016. Medium-sized forest snails survive passage through birds' digestive tract and adhere strongly to birds' legs: More evidence for passive dispersal mechanisms. *Journal of Molluscan Studies* **82**: 422–426. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mollus/eyw005>
- SOLHØY T. 1981. Terrestrial invertebrates of the Faroe Islands: IV. Slugs and snails (Gastropoda): Checklist, distribution, and habitats. *Fauna norvegica* **2**: 14–27. <https://doi.org/10.5324/fn.v2i0.6145>
- THORSTEINSSON K. 2020. Seyður og seyðamark [Sheep and sheep mark]. Búnaðargrunnurin, Tórshavn: Faroe Islands. [In Faroese.]
- VEIHE A, THERS M. 2007. Pedogenesis and root development in a complex geomorphologic setting of the Faroe Islands. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis* **38**: 293–314. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00103620601172266>
- VERBRUGGE LN, BJARNASON G, FAGERHOLM N, MAGNUSSEN E, MORTENSEN L, OLSEN E, PLEININGER T, RAYMOND CM, OLAFSSON AS. 2022. Navigating overgrazing and cultural values through narratives and participatory mapping: a socio-cultural analysis of sheep grazing in the Faroe Islands. *Ecosystems and People* **18**: 289–302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/26395916.2022.2067242>
- WICKHAM H. 2016. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag, New York. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.

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